

Mitigation of Harmonic Distortions in Low Voltage Distribution Grids with Fair Utilization of Resources

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Abstract—Harmonic distortions have adverse effects on the operation of the power system. Harmonic sources in low voltage distribution grids (LVDG) are highly dispersed in nature. Therefore, managing the resulting voltage and current distortions through conventional measures, such as passive or active power filters, becomes challenging. This work coordinates the harmonic injection capabilities of enhanced photovoltaic inverters to form a distributed active power filter. The proposed method aims to reduce the voltage and current distortions of the LVDG with fair utilization of inverters. Towards this direction, a lexicographic optimization scheme is formulated to derive the inverters' harmonic current set-points by (i) minimizing the harmonic voltage limit violations, (ii) maximizing the inverter utilization fairness based on Jain's fairness index, and (iii) minimizing the compensating currents of the inverters to reduce their lifetime degradation. The resulting optimization model is non-convex, thus a convex second-order cone program (SOCP) is formulated by relaxing the non-convex constraints and reformulating the Jain's index as an SOCP constraint. Moreover, an iterative algorithm is developed to find the feasible operating point that maximizes the Jain's fairness value. Simulation results indicate the superiority of the proposed scheme compared to existing methodologies in mitigating harmonic distortions in three-phase four-wire LVDGs.

Index Terms—Convex optimization, harmonic distortion, Jain's fairness index, low-voltage distribution grid, power quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE proliferation of non-linear electronic-based loads in low voltage distribution grids (LVDG) introduces considerable harmonic distortions [1] with several negative impacts on the operation of the distribution grid [2]. Specifically, the effects of harmonic currents are: degradation of power quality, overloading of neutral conductors, increased transformer losses, electromagnetic interference, and equipment degradation [3]. Furthermore, the flow of harmonic current induces voltage distortions, which can adversely affect the operation of appliances and equipment in LVDGs [4].

The literature for harmonic mitigation can be classified into three categories. The first category considers passive filters with the majority of relevant works focused on their optimal sizing and optimal placement [5]. This category also includes

This work was supported in part by the Republic of Cyprus and the Research and Innovation Foundation of Cyprus under the Grant Agreement ENTERPRISES/ENERGY/1123/15 (GridEye) through the Recovery and Resilience Facility (NextGenerationEU); in part by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement 101136119 (TwinEU); and in part by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739551 (KIOS CoE) and from the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy.

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the non-standard zig-zag transformers [6] that can be used for the mitigation of zero-sequence currents at the distribution transformer. In the second category, active power filters (APF) are deployed as they can eliminate positive and negative sequence harmonics [7]. The operation of the APF requires the knowledge of the load current [4] and standalone APFs are typically used at a substation level or near large and highly non-linear loads. Considering that in LVDGs the harmonic sources are highly dispersed, the use of passive filters or APFs in a single location is limited by a low effectiveness or becomes highly expensive when installed at multiple locations. The third category, which is currently the main research focus, considers the new generation multi-functional inverters [8]. In general, PV inverters in LVDGs operate below their nominal capacity and the remaining margin can be utilized for harmonic compensation.

The challenge of harmonic resonance between the inverter's control system and the passive elements of the power system are addressed in [9], [10] to enable its stable operation under a distorted grid voltage. Similarly, in [11] the internal control of the inverter is improved to enhance the quality of the injected power under harmonic distorted grid voltage conditions. The works presented in [9]–[11] ensure the stable and high power quality operation of the inverter-based generation under abnormal grid voltage conditions; however, they do not provide active mitigation of the harmonic distortions introduced by other loads that deteriorate the power quality of the grid. Local [12], [13] and decentralized [14] control schemes to mitigate harmonic distortions utilizing PV inverters as APFs have been proposed. However, the uncoordinated operation of local control schemes can result in non-effective solutions [15]. Specifically, the prevalence of mainly single-phase PV inverters that are coupled by the neutral wire is typically neglected in local-based control schemes. Therefore, optimization schemes can be developed to effectively manage the PV inverters for harmonic mitigation in LVDGs.

Optimization schemes for harmonic mitigation are presented in [16]–[21]. A decentralized multi-objective optimization problem is formulated in [16] that minimizes the voltage unbalance factor and the total voltage harmonic distortion; however, this method is applicable only to islanded low voltage microgrids and it considers only three-phase inverters. A distributed method based on model predictive control for minimizing the harmonic voltage distortions through the calculation of the inverters' virtual conductance is presented in [17]; however, this method has been developed for three-phase three-wire medium voltage distribution grids. In [18], an unconstrained optimization model is proposed to minimize voltage distortions and the voltage unbalance through APFs; however, the constraints of the total harmonic distortion

(THD) and the APF capacity are ignored. A particle swarm optimization method that schedules the operation of energy storage systems to minimize the network's voltage THD and operational costs is proposed in [19]; however, this method may result in high execution times, especially in large distribution grids [22]. In [20], an optimization scheme is developed to minimize grid power losses and voltage unbalance as well as voltage distortion considering the optimal power flow (OPF) in three-phase three-wire networks. This scheme deals with the non-convex OPF model by convexifying the original non-convex problem, which is hard to solve, into a semidefinite program; however, it neglects the neutral coupling that exists in three-phase four-wire LVDGs. Similarly, the harmonic mitigation strategy in [21] handles the non-convex OPF model by transforming the original problem into a convex quadratic constrained quadratic program by replacing power flow equations with current injection equations.

The aforementioned schemes in [16]–[21] have two main practical limitations when they are applied to LVDGs. Firstly, the existing background harmonic distortion that propagates from the upstream network is not taken into account. Specifically, the harmonic distortions that propagate from the medium voltage grid can be the dominant factor in LVDGs [23], especially near the secondary substation. Secondly, optimization schemes that minimize voltage distortions unnecessarily overutilize the inverters, which reduces their expected lifetime [24]. This occurs as these methods aim to fully compensate the harmonic distortions rather than ensuring compliance with the regulatory limits. Furthermore, a highly non-uniform inverter utilization is obtained from [17]–[21] when applied to LVDGs with background harmonic distortions. The resulting non-uniform inverter lifetime degradation can therefore incur an unfair replacement cost.

A proportionally equal usage of the inverters' capacity yields a fair uniform lifetime degradation. However, this is not always ideal as it can cause excessive harmonic currents at the transformer with negative impacts on its lifetime. Furthermore, it can also hinder the management of voltage distortions within the regulatory limits. Therefore, the inverters utilization fairness must first be quantified and then maximized considering the network integrity. Towards this direction, the widely-used Jain's fairness index [25] is utilized in this work. Jain's fairness index has been used extensively in communication systems [26], [27] to ensure that the resource allocation between different users satisfies a minimum fairness threshold. For power systems, Jain's index has been used in [28]–[30] to evaluate the resulting fairness of PV curtailments, the usage of a community-based storage system, and the energy allocation to electric vehicles considering different objective functions.

This work proposes a centralized harmonic mitigation scheme (CHMS) for managing the current set-points of PV inverters to improve the power quality in LVDGs. Specifically, the CHMS restrains the voltage distortions at the end-users and the harmonic current at the transformer within specified limits. Towards this direction, a novel lexicographic¹ optimization scheme is formulated that derives the inverter's set-points to (i) minimize the harmonic voltage limit violations of the

LVDG, (ii) maximize the fair utilization of inverters by utilizing the Jain's fairness index, and (iii) minimize the inverters' compensating currents to reduce their lifetime degradation. This work penalizes the harmonic voltage violations, instead of minimizing the voltage distortion, to avoid the overusage of inverters. In addition, the CHMS considers the particularities of three-phase four-wire LVDGs, such as the neutral coupling and background harmonic distortions, thus enabling a more effective and efficient power quality improvement.

The resulting optimization problem is non-convex, which is challenging to solve, due to the maximization of the Jain's fairness index and the harmonic flow equations. To address this issue, convexification is used to transform the non-convex model to a convex second-order cone program (SOCP), which converges with a high computational efficiency. Specifically, the objective function that maximizes the Jain's index is reformulated as an SOCP constraint with a minimum fairness value. Moreover, the harmonic flow equations are reformulated in rectangular coordinates to eliminate the trigonometric functions of phase angles. The resulting constraint of the harmonic current magnitude is non-convex and hence is relaxed to an SOCP constraint. The SOCP model yields optimal solutions when the relaxed harmonic current constraint is exact; however, non-exact solutions are generated when the fairness constraint cannot be satisfied. Therefore, an iterative algorithm based on the bisection method is developed to find the feasible operating point, i.e., an exact solution is obtained, that maximizes the Jain's fairness value. In summary, this work has three main contributions:

- 1) Development of a novel scheme for coordinating PV inverters to mitigate harmonic voltage violations within the LVDG and restrict the harmonic current at the transformer. The CHMS minimizes the harmonic voltage violations, maximizes the fair utilization of inverters, and minimizes the inverter usage in a lexicographic fashion.
- 2) The proposed CHMS considers the particularities of three-phase four wire LVDGs such as the neutral coupling and background harmonic distortions, enabling more effective and efficient power quality improvement.
- 3) A novel solution methodology is developed based on a convex lexicographic optimization scheme, enabling a high computational efficiency. The harmonic current constraints are relaxed and the objective function of the Jain's fairness index is reformulated to SOCP constraints. Furthermore, an iterative algorithm to find the feasible operating point, relaxed constraints are exact, that maximizes the utilization fairness of inverters is developed.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II the system and control architecture are described. Section III states the examined problem and Section IV describes the proposed solution methodology. Simulation results are shown in Section V and the paper concludes in Section VI.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

A typical single-line diagram of a LVDG that consists of residential dwellings and multi-functional PV inverters is illustrated in Fig. 1. Let $h \in \mathcal{H} = [3, 5, 7, \dots, H]$ denote the low-order harmonic frequencies with H being the highest harmonic frequency being considered, $k \in \mathcal{K} = [1, \dots, K]$

¹A lexicographic optimization problem optimizes L objective functions, $f_l(\mathbf{x})$ $l = 1, \dots, L$, on a feasible set $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$ in a *lexicographic order* such that $f_l(\mathbf{x})$ has higher priority than $f_{l+1}(\mathbf{x})$, see Appendix A.

Fig. 1. Harmonic distortions in LVDGs.

Fig. 2. Main components of the CHMS and their interaction.

represent the system nodes, $p \in \mathcal{P} = [a, b, c]$ denote the system phases with $\mathcal{P}_k \subseteq \mathcal{P}$ defined as the available phases at node k , and sets $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{K}$ and $\mathcal{M}_g \subseteq \mathcal{P}$, $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $m \in \mathcal{M}_g$ denote the nodes and phases, respectively, that contain the multi-functional inverters.

The root mean square (RMS) of the h -th harmonic voltage $V_{h,k,p}$ at the point of connection of the end-user at node k and phase p has two main sources of distortion. The first source is the voltage distortion caused by the harmonic voltage drop across the grid impedance of the LVDG due to the collective flow of harmonic current from all dwellings. The non-linear loads from each dwelling inject a harmonic current I_h^L , contributing to the first source of voltage distortion. The second source of voltage distortion in LVDGs is the harmonic distortion at the secondary substation V_h^{SS} that propagates from the MV grid. The overall harmonic distortion at the end-users can exceed the regulation limits, adversely affecting the operation of the residential devices [4]. In addition, since the harmonic phase angles in residential LVDGs are distributed within a narrow band [3], [23], the harmonic injections from each dwelling tend to be additive. This cumulative effect can lead to a significant RMS harmonic current $I_{h,p}^q$ at the transformer.

A. CHMS Control Architecture

A grid-level controller is utilized to realize the proposed CHMS for effective harmonic mitigation in LVDGs, with its main components and their interactions illustrated in Fig. 2. The grid-level controller regulates the harmonic current injection of the multi-functional (noted as MF in Fig. 2) inverters by deriving their phasor² control set-points $I_{h,g,m}$ (output), considering the harmonic voltages at the end-users and the harmonic currents at the transformer (inputs). The harmonic voltage phasor $\dot{V}_{h,k,p}^V$ at each active end-user equipped

²A phasor \dot{Z} is a complex number which is defined by its magnitude Z and angle θ_z and is expressed as $\dot{Z} = Z(\cos\theta_z + jsin\theta_z)$. The squared phasor magnitude can be expressed as $Z^2 = \Re(\dot{Z})^2 + \Im(\dot{Z})^2$.

Fig. 3. Grid connection of a multi-functional inverter and its simplified control block diagram with the addition of the proposed CHMS capability.

with a multi-functional inverter is extracted by the inverter's controller while the harmonic current phasor $\dot{I}_{h,p}^q$ at the transformer is measured by a smart meter with power quality analyzer capabilities [31].

Power Quality Analyzer: To realize the proposed CHMS, a power quality analyzer is required at the transformer of the LVDG, as depicted in Fig. 1. The power quality analyzer samples the per-phase current at the transformer and extracts its harmonic components $\dot{I}_{h,p}^q$, RMS value and phase angle, typically through the use of a fast Fourier transform algorithm. According to the standard IEC 61000-4-7, which defines requirements for harmonic measurements, the power quality analyzer utilizes a time window of 10 cycles to accurately compute the harmonic components. Therefore, it can provide updated measurements as fast as every 0.2 s in a 50 Hz system. Furthermore, the phase angles of the harmonic components extracted by the power quality analyzer consider the fundamental voltage component as the reference vector. As indicated in Fig. 2, the power quality analyzer has a one-way communication link with the grid controller. At each control step t_{cs} , the power quality analyzer sends to the grid controller $6N_h$ measurements consisting of the RMS harmonic current and its corresponding phase angle at each phase, where N_h is the number of harmonic frequencies that are being considered.

Multi-Functional Inverters: The grid connection of a multi-functional inverter and its simplified control block diagram adopting the CHMS is illustrated in Fig. 3. For its reliable operation, the inverter can utilize the local voltage measurements v_{ac} to extract the fundamental \dot{V}_f and harmonic frequency components $\dot{V}_{h,k,p}^V$ through a dynamic analysis and decomposition using an advanced phase locked loop approach [11], [32]. The multi-functional inverters and the grid controller have a two-way communication link. The harmonic voltage components $\dot{V}_{h,k,p}^V$, including their RMS value and phase angle relative to the fundamental voltage, are forwarded to the grid controller. Then, the inverter receives by the grid controller its corresponding harmonic current set-points $I_{h,g,m}$, as determined by the proposed CHMS. The harmonic set-points and the calculated inverter fundamental current \dot{I}_f as well as the voltage components \dot{V}_f and $\dot{V}_{h,k,p}^V$ are utilized by the enhanced current controller [11], [32]. This enables the determination of the inverter reference voltage \dot{V}^* , allowing the accurate injection of both fundamental and harmonic currents. The reference voltage is then used to generate the pulse width modulation (PWM) signals of the

inverter's switching elements.

Grid Controller: The grid controller assigns priority in the operation of the inverters at fundamental frequency (e.g., for injecting the produced PV power); therefore, it utilizes only the remaining inverter capacity for harmonic mitigation. The CHMS scheme is executed at each control step t_{cs} to derive new inverters' control set-points based on the real-time operating conditions, captured by the input measurements from the power quality analyzer and the multi-functional inverters. Note that CHMS is based on a convex optimization scheme which can be fast and reliably solved, enabling a fast control step in the scale of a few seconds, allowing to timely and dynamically compensate harmonic distortions. At each control step, the grid controller receives $2N_h(3 + N_g)$ measurements, consisting of RMS values and phase angles, from the power quality analyzer and the multi-functional inverters, where N_g is the number of single-phase inverters. The grid controller then sends in total $2N_h N_g$ set-points to the inverters consisting of the RMS value and phase angle of the desired inverter output current at the considered harmonic frequencies.

B. Practical Requirements

Inverter Accessibility: The CHMS utilizes the available inverter capacity in residential LVDGs to improve the power quality. However, this requires that the inverters, which are owned by different end-users, are accessible by the grid controller. Towards this direction, an ancillary services market framework in active distribution grids [33] can provide incentives to the end-users, such as remuneration for participating in the CHMS, in return for access to their inverters.

Furthermore, multi-functional inverters that participate in the CHMS should be equipped with a third-party interface that enables the exchange of measurements and set-points with the grid controller. Note that such interfaces are already available in commercial inverters, e.g., inverter solutions by SMA Solar or Fronius, and are typically based on either Modbus TCP protocols or over-the-internet communication for managing the operation of the inverter at fundamental frequency. Therefore, these third-party interfaces need to be extended by inverter manufacturers to include the inverter management at harmonic frequencies, enabling the practical implementation of such harmonic mitigation schemes.

Communication Network: The proposed CHMS requires a one-way communication link between the power quality analyzer and the grid controller as well as a two-way communication link between the multi-functional inverters and the grid controller. Overall, the data exchange between the different components at each control step is limited, thus introducing only a marginal communication burden. Furthermore, technological advancements and the mass adoption of new communication technologies can enable cloud-based internet-of-things (IoT) platforms. These platforms can provide fast, reliable, and secure communication in distribution grids for real-time applications [34], such as the proposed CHMS, using encrypted protocols like MQTT or HTTPS.

For integrating the power quality analyzer and the inverters in the CHMS, there are two practical options: (i) direct integration when the power quality analyzer and the inverters support third-party interfaces based on application programming interface (API) via encrypted and over-the-internet communication,

(ii) indirect integration when the power quality analyzer and the inverters support only unencrypted interfaces, such as those based on Modbus. In the latter case, a local hub (gateway) is needed to facilitate a seamless data-exchange by translating the local measurements/set-points from unencrypted protocols into encrypted APIs, enabling a secure and over-the-internet communication. Any potential errors and faults in the communication network may affect the performance of any centralized/distributed method; however, this is out of the scope of this work.

THD Limit of the Inverter's Current: The inverter current has typically a 5% THD limit, set by the grid regulations, to ensure adequate power quality when the inverter is viewed as an undesirable and uncontrollable harmonic source. However, when operating the multi-functional inverters as an APF to mitigate the harmonic distortions affecting the grid, their output current might need to exceed the 5% THD limit. Therefore, for an effective inverter-based harmonic mitigation strategy in LVDGs, this restriction should not apply to multi-functional inverters when they operate as an APF.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The proposed CHMS aims to improve the power quality in LVDGs with fair utilization of the available inverters. In contrast to [18]–[21] where voltage distortions are minimized with an overusage of the inverters, CHMS utilizes the inverters to restraint voltage distortions and the harmonic currents at the transformer within specified limits. However, the voltage distortion limits may not be ensured under specific network conditions and inverters' availability. Therefore, to ensure a feasible solution, CHMS manages the harmonic current injection by the inverters in a lexicographic fashion to: (i) minimize harmonic voltage violations, (ii) maximize the fair utilization of the inverters, and (iii) minimize the inverters' compensating currents.

A. Objective Function

The proposed lexicographic problem CHMS comprises three objective functions, denoted as f_V , f_J , f_I . These objective functions are optimized in a *lexicographic order*, see Appendix A, where first priority is given in f_V to minimize the harmonic voltages that exceed the limits. Then, the inverter utilization fairness f_J is maximized ensuring the voltage violations obtained from the solution of the first optimization subproblem. Finally, the harmonic current contribution by the inverters f_I is minimized.

This work defines the lexicographic order based on the importance of the three objectives. Note that several standards, such as EN 50160, define permissible limits for harmonic voltage distortions in distribution grids to ensure adequate power quality for end-users. Therefore, the operation of the distribution grid within the harmonic voltage distortion limits is critical and hence a first priority is given to f_V . Considering that the mitigation of harmonic voltage distortions by optimizing objective f_V may lead to the over-utilization of the inverters located closer to the transformer, resulting in non-uniform inverter lifetime degradation, second priority is given to f_J . Specifically, the inverter utilization fairness is maximized by ensuring the minimum harmonic voltage limit

violations obtained from the minimization of objective f_V , resulting to a near uniform inverter lifetime degradation. Note that, if second priority is given to f_I , the inverter utilization fairness will be restricted to a low value, corresponding to the minimum inverter currents, without the possibility of increasing as this would affect the optimality of f_I . Hence, a third priority is given to f_I to minimize the inverters' compensating currents, reducing their lifetime degradation, by ensuring the minimum harmonic voltage limit violations and maximum fairness value obtained from the optimization of objectives f_V and f_J . Note that the minimization of objective f_I is necessary because the maximum fairness value can be achieved under different inverter currents (multiple solutions). **Harmonic Voltage Limit Violation Function:** CHMS generates feasible solutions under any operating conditions and inverter availability that improve the power quality. This is achieved by minimizing the squared value of the harmonic voltages that exceed the specified limits, defined as

$$f_V(\mathbf{v}) = \sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_k} \left(V_{h,k,p}^+ \right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where variables $V_{h,k,p}^+ \geq 0$ denote the harmonic voltage limit violation of the h -th harmonic at the k -th node and phase p , while \mathbf{v} denotes the vector-form of $V_{h,k,p}^+$ for all $h \in \mathcal{H}$, $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $p \in \mathcal{P}_k$.

Inverter's Utilization Fairness Function: The fairness of the inverters' utilization is quantitatively expressed by using the Jain's fairness index [25], [26], given by

$$f_J(\mathbf{i}) = \frac{\left(\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} \hat{I}_{g,m} / \bar{I}_{g,m}^H \right)^2}{N_g \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} \left(\hat{I}_{g,m} / \bar{I}_{g,m}^H \right)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where constants N_g and $\bar{I}_{g,m}^H$ denote the total number of inverters and the current capacity for harmonic compensation of the inverter connected to node g and phase m . Variables $\hat{I}_{g,m}$ denote the inverter RMS compensation current, expressed as the true RMS value considering all harmonic frequencies except the fundamental [35], defined as

$$\hat{I}_{g,m} = \sqrt{\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} (I_{h,g,m})^2}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, m \in \mathcal{M}_g, \quad (3)$$

where variables $I_{h,g,m}$ denote the RMS current of the h -th harmonic frequency. Furthermore, \mathbf{i} denotes the vector-form of variable $I_{h,g,m}$ for all $h \in \mathcal{H}$, $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $m \in \mathcal{M}_g$. The inverters' utilization fairness (2) is evaluated based on the relative usage of each inverter's available capacity $\bar{I}_{g,m}^H$. Function $f_J(\mathbf{i})$ takes values in the range $[1/N_g, 1]$, where $f_J(\mathbf{i}) = 1/N_g$ is the worst case where only one inverter is deployed while $f_J(\mathbf{i}) = 1$ is the best case where all inverters are equally utilized.

Inverters' Harmonic Current Function: The inverters' total harmonic current function is defined as the summation of the RMS compensation current provided by all inverters

$$f_I(\mathbf{i}) = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} \hat{I}_{g,m}. \quad (4)$$

Objective Function: The objective function of the proposed lexicographic problem CHMS is defined as

$$\text{lexmin} \quad \{f_V(\mathbf{v}), -f_J(\mathbf{i}), f_I(\mathbf{i})\} \quad (5)$$

B. Constraints

Harmonic Voltage Limits: The soft constraint that restrains the harmonic voltages within the limits is set as

$$V_{h,k,p} \leq \bar{V}_h + V_{h,k,p}^+, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}, k \in \mathcal{K}, p \in \mathcal{P}_k, \quad (6)$$

where variables $V_{h,k,p}$ denote the phase-neutral voltage magnitude of the h -th harmonic frequency at node k and phase p . Constant \bar{V}_h denotes the harmonic voltage limit for the h -th harmonic frequency. The harmonic voltage limit \bar{V}_h can be specified based on relevant grid codes or standards such as the EN 50160. Note that the minimization of the summation of squares of $V_{h,k,p}^+$ in (1) restrains the harmonic voltages in (6) within the limits, such that $V_{h,k,p}^+ = 0$, when there is sufficient available capacity from the inverters. Otherwise, the harmonic voltage limit violations are minimized to achieve a feasible solution that improves the power quality.

Inverter Capacity Limits: CHMS assigns priority in the operation of the inverters at fundamental frequency, allowing the inverter to continue its business as usual (BAU) operation. To avoid overloading the inverters, their harmonic currents are restricted by their remaining available capacity, given by

$$\hat{I}_{g,m} \leq \bar{I}_{g,m}^H, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, m \in \mathcal{M}_g, \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{I}_{g,m}^H = \sqrt{\left(\bar{I}_{g,m}^R \right)^2 - (P_{g,m}^2 + Q_{g,m}^2) / V_{g,m}^2}$. Constants $\bar{I}_{g,m}^R$ denote the rated current of the inverter at node g and phase m , $P_{g,m}$ and $Q_{g,m}$ the active and reactive power output of the inverter at fundamental frequency for the BAU operation, and $V_{g,m}$ the fundamental phase-neutral RMS voltage at the PCC of the inverter. Note that $P_{g,m}$, $Q_{g,m}$, and $V_{g,m}$ are used to determine the inverter RMS current at the fundamental frequency and are considered known by the grid management. Otherwise, the fundamental RMS current, $I_{g,m}^F$, can be sent directly by the inverters to the CHMS grid controller, such that $\bar{I}_{g,m}^H = \sqrt{\left(\bar{I}_{g,m}^R \right)^2 - (I_{g,m}^F)^2}$.

Three-Phase Three-Wire Inverters: Although single-phase inverters are more common in LV DGs, three-phase three-wire inverters are also included for generality. Let $\mathcal{W} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$ denote the subset that contains the nodes that have three-phase inverters. The absence of a neutral wire in such inverters imposes the constraint that the summation of the three-phase current phasors for each harmonic frequency must be equal to zero, given by

$$\sum_{g \in \mathcal{W}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} \hat{I}_{h,g,m} = 0, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}, \quad (8)$$

where variable $\hat{I}_{h,g,m}$ is the inverter current phasor for the h -th harmonic frequency. Note that variable $I_{h,g,m}$ is the magnitude of phasor $\hat{I}_{h,g,m}$. Furthermore, a three-phase four-wire inverter can also be included as three independent single-phase inverters that are not restricted by constraint (8).

Distribution Transformer Harmonic Current: A high harmonic current at the distribution transformer increases its electrical stress with a negative impact on its lifetime. To avoid a transformer derating, the proposed method limits

the equivalent total harmonic RMS current at the MV-LV transformer, node 1, given by

$$\hat{I}_p^t = \sqrt{\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \left(I_{h,p}^t \right)^2}, \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}_k, \quad (9a)$$

$$\hat{I}_p^t \leq \alpha_p \bar{I}^t, \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}_k \quad (9b)$$

where variables $I_{h,p}^t$ and \hat{I}_p^t denote the h -th harmonic RMS current at phase p at the distribution transformer and the overall RMS current, respectively. Constant $0 \leq \alpha_p \leq 1$ denotes the tuneable parameter that controls the allowable harmonic current at phase p in relation to the transformer's per-phase rated current \bar{I}^t . To ensure the feasibility of constraint (9b), α_p is set as $\alpha_p = \max\{\alpha_s, \hat{\alpha}_p\}$ where parameter α_s is the desired value for α_p . Constant $\hat{\alpha}_p$ is calculated based on the lowest feasible harmonic current at phase p of the distribution transformer and is updated in each execution of CHMS based on the operating conditions. Therefore, when the transformer current cannot be reduced to $\alpha_s \bar{I}^t$, constraint (9b) remains feasible as α_p is updated to $\hat{\alpha}_p$. Note that the calculation of the distribution transformer current $I_{h,p}^t$ requires either an explicit knowledge of the harmonic current of each load or that a power quality analyzer is installed at the transformer. In the proposed CHMS scheme, the harmonic content of the load current is considered unknown as additional sensors to each dwelling are required, which can be restrictive for its wide applicability. Instead, a power quality analyzer is utilized to measure and directly extract the harmonic components of the grid current at the distribution transformer. Examples of low-cost power quality analyzers can be found in [31]. Utilizing the power quality analyzer, the distribution transformer current for harmonic frequency h is calculated as,

$$\hat{I}_{h,p}^t = \hat{I}_{h,p}^q + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \Delta \hat{I}_{h,g,m}, \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}_k, m = p, \quad (10a)$$

$$\hat{I}_{h,g,m} = \hat{I}_{h,g,m}^o + \Delta \hat{I}_{h,g,m}, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, m \in \mathcal{M}_g, \quad (10b)$$

where input $\hat{I}_{h,p}^q$ denotes the phasor measurement of the transformer current. Variables $\hat{I}_{h,p}^t$ denote the transformer current phasor ($I_{h,p}^t$ is the magnitude of $\hat{I}_{h,p}^t$) and $\Delta \hat{I}_{h,g,m}$ denotes the variation of $\hat{I}_{h,g,m}$ which is induced by CHMS in the current control step in relation to the previous control set-points, which are denoted by $\hat{I}_{h,g,m}^o$ (CHMS output from the previous control step).

Harmonic Flow Equations: This work utilizes the advanced capabilities of the new generation of multi-functional inverters to derive harmonic flow equations that are independent of the load current. A smart inverter can measure and extract the harmonic voltage spectrum at its PCC for its internal control functionality [12]. By providing this information to the grid controller it allows to derive harmonic flow equations to relate the harmonic phase-neutral voltages with the flow of harmonic current for all $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $p \in \mathcal{P}_k$, $h \in \mathcal{H}$, given by

$$\dot{V}_{h,k,p} = \dot{V}_{h,k,p}^V + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}, m=p} Z_h^t \Delta \hat{I}_{h,g,m} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} Z_{h,k,g}^{pm} \Delta \hat{I}_{h,g,m}, \quad (11)$$

where variables $\dot{V}_{h,k,p}$ denote the phase-neutral voltage phasor at node k and phase p for the h -th harmonic frequency ($V_{h,k,p}$

is the magnitude of phasor $\dot{V}_{h,k,p}$) when the CHMS set-points are applied. Input $\dot{V}_{h,k,p}^V$ denotes the phasor measurement of the PCC phase-neutral voltage from the inverter. If node k and phase p does not have a connected inverter, the measurement from the closest inverter connected to phase p , or by the power quality analyzer depending which is closest, can be utilized in place of $\dot{V}_{h,k,p}^V$. This is a close approximation of the harmonic voltage phasor of the absent inverter as the length of the distribution lines are short and in a PV rich network the next available inverter will be in close proximity. Constants $Z_h^t = R^t + jX_h^t$ are the harmonic impedance of the distribution transformer and $Z_{h,k,g}^{pm} = R_{h,k,g}^{pm} + jX_{h,k,g}^{pm}$ is the common³ harmonic line impedance between nodes k, g and phases p, m . The common line impedance between arbitrary nodes k, g and phases p, m , respectively, $Z_{h,k,g}^{pm}$ is calculated through a network analysis incorporating a four-wire distribution line model to account for the neutral coupling, as given by

$$Z_{h,k,g}^{pm} = \begin{cases} z_{h,k,g}^{pp} - 2z_{h,k,g}^{pm} + z_{h,k,g}^{nn}, & m = p, \\ z_{h,k,g}^{pm} - z_{h,k,g}^{pn} - z_{h,k,g}^{nm} + z_{h,k,g}^{nn}, & m \neq p, \end{cases} \quad (12a)$$

$$\sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{kg}} \mathbf{z}_{h,l} = \begin{bmatrix} z_{h,k,g}^{aa} & \cdots & z_{h,k,g}^{an} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ z_{h,k,g}^{na} & \cdots & z_{h,k,g}^{nn} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12b)$$

where $\mathbf{z}_{h,l} \in \mathbb{C}^{4 \times 4}$ is the harmonic impedance matrix [19] for the l -th line segment and \mathcal{L}_{kg} is the set containing all line segments that are common for nodes k, g .

The proposed CHMS scheme derives in each control step the inverters' current set-points $\hat{I}_{h,g,m}$ to minimize objective (5), ensuring constraints (3), (6)-(11). The proposed approach eliminates the need of knowing the load current, where in most cases requires additional sensors to each dwelling, by utilizing the capabilities of multi-functional PV inverters. Furthermore, as the background voltage harmonic distortion is encapsulated by $\dot{V}_{h,n,p}^V$, the proposed CHMS scheme enables a higher power quality improvement in LVDGs, regardless of the operating conditions of the primary distribution grid.

The lexicographic optimization problem that is solved by the grid controller is summarized as

$$\mathbb{P}^E : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & (5) \\ \text{subject to} & (3), (6) - (11). \end{cases}$$

Problem \mathbb{P}^E is nonlinear and non-convex and hence challenging to solve due to (i) the nonlinear and non-convex equality constraints (3) and (9a), (ii) the non-convex constraints (8), (10) and (11) that include voltage and current phasors, and (iii) the maximization of the Jain's fairness index in objective (2) that is nonlinear and non-concave [36]. The aforementioned issues are addressed in the next section.

IV. SOLUTION METHODOLOGY

This section convexifies the original problem by formulating an SOCP optimization model. Moreover, an iterative algorithm is developed to find the feasible operating point, i.e., an exact solution is obtained, that maximizes the Jain's fairness value.

³Common line impedance refers to the line segments that both the current from node k phase p and the current from node g and phase m flow through.

A. Convexifying Problem \mathbb{P}^E

1) *Constraints:* The constraints (8), (10), and (11) are non-convex due to the voltage and current phasors. To eliminate the non-convexity of phasor variables and the trigonometric functions of the phasors' angle, the problem is reformulated in rectangular coordinates. This approach allows to derive linear constraints where the real and imaginary parts of phasor variables can be considered separately. In addition, the Jain's fairness index in objective (2) is reformulated as an SOCP constraint. The real and imaginary parts of phasor variables are denoted by r and x in the superscript, respectively.

Harmonic Flow Equations: Through algebraic analysis of (10b) and (11), linear equality constraints for the network model are introduced for the real and imaginary parts of the considered phasor variables for all $h \in \mathcal{H}$, $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $p \in \mathcal{P}_k$. The real and imaginary parts of the inverter control set-points considering the h -th harmonic for the inverter connected to node g and phase m are given by

$$I_{h,g,m}^r = I_{h,g,m}^{o,r} + \Delta I_{h,g,m}^r, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, m \in \mathcal{M}_g, \quad (13a)$$

$$I_{h,g,m}^x = I_{h,g,m}^{o,x} + \Delta I_{h,g,m}^x, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, m \in \mathcal{M}_g, \quad (13b)$$

where variables $I_{h,g,m}^r$ and $I_{h,g,m}^x$ denote the real and imaginary parts of phasor $\hat{I}_{h,g,m}$, and $I_{h,g,m}^{o,r}$ and $I_{h,g,m}^{o,x}$ denote the real and imaginary parts of the CHMS output from the previous control step $\hat{I}_{h,g,m}^o$. In addition, variables $\Delta I_{h,g,m}^r$ and $\Delta I_{h,g,m}^x$ denote the real and imaginary parts of the control set-point variation $\Delta \hat{I}_{h,g,m}$. The real part of the voltage phasor $\hat{V}_{h,k,p}$ is given by

$$V_{h,k,p}^r = V_{h,k,p}^{V,r} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}, m=p} (R^t \Delta I_{h,g,m}^r - X_h^t \Delta I_{h,g,m}^x) + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} (R_{kg}^{pm} \Delta I_{h,g,m}^r - X_{h,kg}^{pm} \Delta I_{h,g,m}^x), \quad (14)$$

where variables $V_{h,k,p}^r$ and input measurements $V_{h,n,p}^{V,r}$ denote the real part of phasors $\hat{V}_{h,k,p}$ and $\hat{V}_{h,k,p}^V$, respectively. Similarly, the imaginary part of phasor $\hat{V}_{h,k,p}$ is defined as

$$V_{h,k,p}^x = V_{h,k,p}^{V,x} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}, m=p} (R^t \Delta I_{h,g,m}^x + X_h^t \Delta I_{h,g,m}^r) + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} (R_{kg}^{pm} \Delta I_{h,g,m}^x + X_{h,kg}^{pm} \Delta I_{h,g,m}^r), \quad (15)$$

where variables $V_{h,k,p}^x$ and input measurements $V_{h,k,p}^{V,x}$ denote the imaginary part of phasors $\hat{V}_{h,k,p}$ and $\hat{V}_{h,k,p}^V$, respectively.

Operational Constraints: Constraints (6)-(9) presented in Section III-B are reformulated in rectangular coordinates for all $h \in \mathcal{H}$, $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $p \in \mathcal{P}_k$, $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $m \in \mathcal{M}_g$. Towards this direction, constraints (6), (7), and (9) that include the currents and voltages magnitude are reformulated as

Harmonic Voltage Limits:

$$(V_{h,k,p}^r)^2 + (V_{h,k,p}^x)^2 \leq \bar{V}_h^2 + V_{h,k,p}^+. \quad (16a)$$

Inverter Capacity Limits:

$$\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} (I_{h,g,m}^r)^2 + (I_{h,g,m}^x)^2 \leq (\bar{I}_{g,m}^H)^2. \quad (16b)$$

Distribution Transformer Harmonic Current:

$$\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \left(\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \Delta I_{h,g,m}^r + I_{h,p}^{q,r} \right)^2 + \sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \left(\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \Delta I_{h,g,m}^x + I_{h,p}^{q,x} \right)^2 \leq (\alpha_p \bar{I}^t)^2, \quad m = p, \quad (16c)$$

where inputs $I_{h,p}^{q,r}$, $I_{h,p}^{q,x}$ are the real and imaginary parts of the harmonic current phasor $\hat{I}_{h,p}^q$ at the MV/LV transformer, as measured by the power quality analyzer. Note that constraint (16b) is derived by (3), (7), while constraint (16c) is derived by (9), (10). The three-phase three-wire inverter constraint in (8) is reformulated as

$$\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} I_{h,g,m}^r = 0, \quad \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} I_{h,g,m}^x = 0, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{W}. \quad (17)$$

Jain's Fairness Constraint: The Jain's fairness index in objective (2), which is nonlinear and non-concave [36], is reformulated to an SOCP constraint, given by

$$\frac{\left(\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} \hat{I}_{g,m} / \bar{I}_{g,m}^H \right)^2}{N_g \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} \left(\hat{I}_{g,m} / \bar{I}_{g,m}^H \right)^2} \geq J_0, \quad (18)$$

where constant $1/N_g \leq J_0 \leq 1$ denotes the minimum value of desired fairness. Constraint (18) ensures a level of inverter utilization fairness at least as good as J_0 . Note that constraint (18) is active and hence the inverter utilization fairness is equal to J_0 when the equality is attained in (18); otherwise, constraint (18) is inactive and hence the inverter utilization fairness is greater than J_0 , which can be presented under small values of J_0 . Constraint (18) is equivalently reformulated as

$$Y = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} \hat{I}_{g,m} / \bar{I}_{g,m}^H, \quad (19a)$$

$$Y^2 \geq J_0 N_g \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} \left(\hat{I}_{g,m} / \bar{I}_{g,m}^H \right)^2, \quad (19b)$$

where Y is an auxiliary variable. Constraints (19a) and (19b) are linear and SOCP constraints, respectively. The total inverter RMS harmonic current $\hat{I}_{g,m}$ that is presented in (19) and expressed in rectangular coordinates for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $m \in \mathcal{M}_g$ is given by

$$\left(\hat{I}_{g,m} \right)^2 = \sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} (I_{h,g,m}^r)^2 + (I_{h,g,m}^x)^2. \quad (20)$$

Constraint (20) is a nonlinear equality constraint and hence non-convex. To convexify the considered problem, the non-convex constraint (20) is relaxed to an SOCP constraint for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $m \in \mathcal{M}_g$, defined as

$$\left(\hat{I}_{g,m} \right)^2 \geq \sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} (I_{h,g,m}^r)^2 + (I_{h,g,m}^x)^2. \quad (21)$$

The relaxation exactness is satisfied when the equality is attained in (21); otherwise, the obtained solution is infeasible for the original problem.

B. Lexicographic Optimization

Considering the Jain's fairness index as a convex SOCP constraint with a given value of fairness J_0 , instead of an objective function, the three-objectives non-convex lexicographic optimization of Section III is reformulated as a two-objectives convex lexicographic optimization scheme. Specifically, the first optimization subproblem minimizes the harmonic voltage violations, while the second optimization subproblem minimizes the inverters harmonic currents considering the Jain's fairness constraint. The two optimization subproblems of the two-objectives lexicographic scheme are the following.

Problem \mathbb{P}^V : The first optimization subproblem minimizes the squared value of the harmonic voltages that exceed the limits considering the harmonic flow and operational constraints, formulated as

$$\mathbb{P}^V : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & (1) \\ \text{subject to} & (13) - (17). \end{cases}$$

Problem \mathbb{P}^V is a convex quadratically constrained quadratic program which can be fast, reliably, and optimally solved. Note that Problem \mathbb{P}^V is independent of the fairness constraints and therefore there are no relaxation violation issues because constraint (21) is ignored.

Problem \mathbb{P}^I : The second optimization subproblem minimizes the total harmonic currents of the inverters considering as constraints the: (i) operational and harmonic flow equations, (ii) minimum desired fairness value J_0 , and (iii) harmonic voltage violations resulted from the solution of the first subproblem \mathbb{P}^V , formulated as

$$\mathbb{P}^I : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & (4) \\ \text{subject to} & (13) - (17), (19a), (19b), (21), \\ & V_{h,k,p}^+ \leq \hat{V}_{h,k,p}^+, \forall h \in \mathcal{H}, k \in \mathcal{K}, p \in \mathcal{P}_k, \end{cases}$$

where constants $\hat{V}_{h,k,p}^+$ denote the harmonic voltage violations obtained from the solution of \mathbb{P}^V . The control set-points that are submitted to the inverters are the reference currents $I_{h,g,m}^r$ and $I_{h,g,m}^x$. Problem \mathbb{P}^I is a convex SOCP program which can be fast, reliably, and optimally solved. The minimization of the inverters RMS harmonic current $\hat{I}_{g,m}$ in objective (4) is an incentive to satisfy the relaxation exactness of constraint (21). Moreover, the minimization of $\hat{I}_{g,m}$ causes the tightness of constraint (19b), the constraint is active, because the increment of the inverter utilization fairness results in an increased current from the inverters. The proper selection of the fairness parameter $J_0 \in [1/N_g, 1]$ in constraint (19b) is critical because high values are desirable to increase the inverters utilization fairness but may yield infeasible solutions, relaxation violation of constraint (21), when the desired fairness value cannot be achieved under the specific operating conditions. This issue is addressed in the next section.

C. Maximizing Inverters' Utilization Fairness

This section develops an iterative algorithm based on the bisection method to find the feasible operating point that maximizes the inverters' utilization fairness, defined as Algorithm Max-IUF. Specifically, Algorithm Max-IUF iteratively solves Problem \mathbb{P}^I to find the largest value of $J_0 \in [1/N_g, 1]$ that yields a feasible solution, i.e., exactness of constraint (21).

Algorithm 1 : Max-IUF

```

1: Input:  $e$ .
2: Init.  $J_{lb} = 1/N_g, J_{ub} = 1$ .
3: Solve  $\mathbb{P}^V$  to obtain  $\hat{V}_{h,k,p}^+, \forall h \in \mathcal{H}, k \in \mathcal{K}, p \in \mathcal{P}_k$ .
4: while  $J_{ub} - J_{lb} \geq e$  do
5:   Set  $J_0 = (J_{ub} + J_{lb})/2$ .
6:   Solve  $\mathbb{P}^I$  to obtain  $\mathbf{x}_{J_0}$ .
7:   if constraint (21) is exact then
8:     Set  $J_{lb} = J_0, \hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{x}_{J_0}, J_{max} = J_0$ .
9:   else
10:    Set  $J_{ub} = J_0$ .
11: Return  $\hat{\mathbf{x}}, J_{max}$ .

```

Algorithm 1 summarizes the proposed procedure utilizing Problems \mathbb{P}^V and \mathbb{P}^I . Initially, the lower and upper bounds, J_{lb} and J_{ub} , for the fairness value J_0 are determined (Line 2) and Problem \mathbb{P}^V is solved to obtain $\hat{V}_{h,k,p}^+$ for all $h \in \mathcal{H}, k \in \mathcal{K}, p \in \mathcal{P}_k$ (Line 3). The iterative process based on the bisection method is presented in Lines 4-10. Specifically, Problem \mathbb{P}^I is solved for $J_0 = (J_{lb} + J_{ub})/2$ to obtain the solution \mathbf{x}_{J_0} (Line 6). Considering that constraint (21) is exact and hence the obtained solution \mathbf{x}_{J_0} is feasible, set $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{x}_{J_0}, J_{max} = J_0$, and $J_{lb} = J_0$ to increase J_0 (Lines 7-8). Otherwise, set $J_{ub} = J_0$ to decrease J_0 when constraint (21) is non-exact (Line 10). Algorithm 1 converges when $J_{ub} - J_{lb}$ becomes smaller than the bisection tolerance e (Line 4), returning the feasible solution $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ obtained for the largest fairness value J_{max} (Line 11). As the searching space is halved at each iteration, the proposed algorithm converges fast.

In summary, using Problems \mathbb{P}^V and \mathbb{P}^I in Algorithm Max-IUF, the proposed CHMS scheme minimizes the harmonic voltage limit violations, maximizes the inverters utilization fairness, and minimizes the inverters harmonic currents in a lexicographic order. Hereafter, the CHMS scheme is referred to the utilization of the convex Problems \mathbb{P}^V and \mathbb{P}^I in Algorithm Max-IUF.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

The performance of the proposed CHMS scheme is examined and compared with a conventional and a literature-based strategy using the test network shown in Fig. 4. The conventional-based strategy, defined as APF strategy, mitigates the harmonic current at the distribution transformer with an equal compensation by the inverters of each phase. The literature-based strategy, defined as min-V, minimizes only the harmonic voltages [20], [21], given by

$$\mathbb{P}^L : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & \sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_k} V_{h,k,p} \\ \text{subject to} & (13) - (15), (16b), (17). \end{cases}$$

The considered network and harmonic mitigation strategies are implemented in MATLAB-Simulink. The optimization problems are solved using the optimization solver Gurobi [37] on a personal computer with 8 GB RAM and an Intel Core-i7 3.2 GHz processor. The bisection tolerance e is set to 0.01.

A. Test Network

The considered network illustrated in Fig. 4 serves 1540 consumers and it consists of 25 passive and 1 simplified active LV feeders. The simplified active LV feeder has been

Fig. 4. Considered distribution grid with an active LVDG.

Fig. 5. Typical time-varying harmonic load profile for a single dwelling, expressed in percentage of the fundamental current.

TABLE I
CONNECTION OF SINGLE-PHASE DWELLINGS AND PV SYSTEMS

Phase	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5	N6	N7	N8	Total
A	1/1	3/1	1/1	3/2	0/0	1/1	2/1	1/0	12/7
B	2/1	1/1	1/1	0/0	3/2	1/0	0/0	2/2	10/7
C	2/1	1/1	3/1	2/0	2/2	3/2	3/2	2/1	18/10

synthesized by analysing several real LV feeders from the Cyprus power system and it consists of 8 load nodes, each hosting 5 single-phase dwellings. Furthermore, the considered active LVDG has in total a main feeder path length of 0.6 km, which is within the typical range for LV feeders, and has a radial configuration which is the standard for most secondary distribution grids [38]. The distribution line model is based on a typical 100 mm² Aluminum over-head line in a vertical configuration. The impedance matrix of the distribution line and the parameters of the distribution transformer are given in Appendix B. The number of dwellings and PV systems in each phase of the 8 load nodes are given in Table I. For instance, at node 3, phase c, there are three dwellings of which only one has a PV system. The overall PV penetration for the considered active LVDG is 60%. The harmonic load spectrum of each dwelling is generated based on real smart meter measurements and the probabilistic models from [39]. In this paper, the 3rd, 5th, and 7th harmonic frequencies are considered as they are the most dominant in residential LVDGs [3]. Nonetheless, it is important to note that additional harmonic frequencies can be readily incorporated in CHMS. The use of the probabilistic models and real smart meter measurements enables the generation of realistic time-varying harmonic load profiles. A typical harmonic load profile for a single dwelling resulting by the considered approach is illustrated in Fig. 5.

The inverter and PV capacity are randomly selected out of three options (i) 2 kVA - 1.5 kW, (ii) 3 kVA - 2.5 kW, and (iii) 5 kVA - 4.25 kW. The single-phase inverters of each phase at each node are replaced with a single inverter with the appropriate sizing (aggregated value), i.e., there are in total

Fig. 6. (a) Overall inverter utilization and (b) actual utilization fairness J_A for different values of J_0 in Problem \mathbb{P}^I .

18 single-phase inverters. The operation of the PV systems at fundamental frequency is computed considering a sunny day and the $\cos\phi(P)$ reactive power provision scheme [15]. The operation of the network is simulated for 24 h and the sampling period and CHMS execution rate t_{cs} is every 20 seconds.

B. Inverters Utilization Fairness

The inverters utilization fairness is investigated by solving Problem \mathbb{P}^I multiple times in a single control step under different values of J_0 . Fig. 6 illustrates the (a) increment of the overall inverters' utilization in percentage based on the available inverters' capacity, and (b) actual inverter utilization fairness J_A when J_0 increases from 0.3 to 1. Specifically, Figs. 6(a) and 6(b) present three distinct regions. In the first region where $J_0 \leq J_{min}$ ($J_{min} = 0.57$), the inverters' utilization and fairness J_A remain constant because the fairness constraint (19b) is inactive and hence $J_A = J_{min}$ for $J_0 \leq 0.57$. Note that J_{min} corresponds to the actual inverter utilization fairness when the fairness constraints (19a) and (19b) are excluded from the formulation of Problem \mathbb{P}^I . In the second region where $J_{min} < J_0 \leq J_{max}$ ($J_{max} = 0.85$), the fairness constraint (19b) is active and hence $J_A = J_0$. Figs. 6(a) and 6(b) show that the increment of the inverters utilization fairness by 49%, from J_{min} to J_{max} , has a small cost on their total utilization which increases by 2%, from 23% to 25%. In the third region where $J_0 > J_{max}$, Problem \mathbb{P}^I yields non-exact solutions, relaxation violation of constraint (21), because the desired fairness value cannot be achieved under the specific operating conditions. Algorithm 1 finds the feasible operating point with the maximum fairness value J_{max} in 8 iterations, resulting in an average execution time of 1.3 seconds.

C. Case 1: Harmonic Mitigation

This case study examines the efficacy of the proposed CHMS scheme in mitigating the harmonic distortions. To ensure compliance with EN 50160 and to demonstrate the capabilities of CHMS, the harmonic voltage limits are set to 2.5% of the nominal voltage of 230 V ($\bar{V}_h = 5.7$ V).

Figs. 7(a.i)-7(d.iii) illustrate the per-phase induced voltage for the 3rd harmonic frequency (Figs. 7(a.i)-7(a.iii)), 5th (Figs. 7(b.i)-7(b.iii)), and 7th (Figs. 7(c.i)-7(c.iii)) as well as the voltage THD⁴ across the active LVDG (Figs. 7(d.i)-7(d.iii)) when

⁴The total harmonic distortion THD [35] at node k and phase p is defined as $THD = \sqrt{\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} (V_{h,k,p})^2} / V_r$. The upper limit of the THD is calculated as $\sqrt{\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} (\bar{V}_h)^2} / V_r$. Note that V_r is the nominal grid voltage.

Fig. 7. Per-phase harmonic voltages and the induced THD without mitigation.

a harmonic mitigation strategy is not considered. The flow of internal harmonic currents and the voltages propagating from the MV to the LV distribution grid cause significant harmonic distortions, which drastically reduce the power quality at the end-users. As shown in Figs. 7(a.i)-7(c.iii), the induced harmonic voltages exceed the limits of 5.7 V, indicating the necessity for a harmonic compensation strategy.

Figs. 8(a.i)-8(d.iii) illustrate the per-phase induced voltage for the 3rd harmonic frequency (Figs. 8(a.i)-8(a.iii)), 5th (Figs. 8(b.i)-8(b.iii)), and 7th (Figs. 8(c.i)-8(c.iii)) as well as the voltage THD (Figs. 8(d.i)-8(d.iii)) when the proposed CHMS scheme with $\alpha_s = 0.03$ is applied. As shown in Figs. 8(a.i)-8(d.iii), the proposed CHMS scheme restraints the voltage distortions within the limits in most cases, enhancing the power quality at the end-users. However, for the load nodes near the transformer, the 5th harmonic voltage limits are frequently violated as the operating conditions prevent further mitigation. In this case, the proposed lexicographic scheme minimizes the harmonic voltages that exceed the limits.

The inverter utilization fairness that is achieved by the CHMS scheme is illustrated in Fig. 9. As shown in the figure, the proposed scheme manages to yield feasible solutions with high inverter utilization fairness J_{max} . Specifically, the CHMS scheme achieves an inverter utilization fairness of $J_{max} \geq 0.95$ in approximately 90% of the considered operating points, ensuring a nearly uniform inverter lifetime degradation.

D. Case 2: Comparison with other Methods

In this case study, the proposed CHMS scheme is compared with the conventional strategy APF and literature-based strategy min-V. Table II shows the average and maximum voltage THD, inverter utilization, fairness index, and total transformer current as defined in (9a), for the considered

Fig. 8. Per-phase harmonic voltages and induced THD using the CHMS.

Fig. 9. Normalized frequency of inverter utilization fairness using the CHMS.

methods. Although the APF approach presents the lowest transformer current and a high average and maximum fairness values, because it equally allocates the compensating currents to the inverters, it yields the highest average and maximum voltage THD at 4.7% and 7.4% V. As shown in Fig. 10, the APF strategy presents high voltage limit violations because it does not consider the background harmonic voltage nor the impact of internal harmonic flows. As shown in Table II, the literature-based strategy min-V yields the lowest average and maximum voltage THD, 0.4% and 3.2% V, because it minimizes the voltage distortions even when the limits are ensured. However, the min-V scheme presents the highest average and maximum transformer current (69 and 97 A) and inverters' utilization (30% and 41%), because it overutilizes the inverters, increasing their lifetime degradation. In contrast, the proposed CHMS scheme reduces the average and maximum transformer current to 29 and 33 A, and reduces the inverters' utilization to 15% and 25% because it minimizes only the harmonic voltage distortions that exceed the limits. In addition, CHMS scheme achieves the highest average and maximum fairness values of 0.97 and 0.99, while maintaining the average voltage THD (3.0% V) within the limits of 4.3%.

TABLE II
COMPARISON BETWEEN DIFFERENT METHODS

Method	THD [%],		Inverter		Fair.		Transf.		Exec.
	limit:	4.3%	util. [%]		index		curr. [A]		
	Avg.	Max	Avg.	Max	Avg.	Max	Avg.	Max	Avg.
No mitig.	7.8	12.7	-	-	-	-	37	49	-
APF	4.7	7.4	10.7	16.2	0.85	0.90	3.2	12	<0.10
min-V	0.4	3.2	30.4	40.6	0.56	0.68	69	97	0.15
CHMS	3.0	5.3	15.1	25.1	0.97	0.99	29	33	1.30

Fig. 10. Fifth harmonic voltage distortion considering the APF strategy.

Fig. 11. Inverter utilization using the (a) min-V and (b) CHMS schemes.

Figs. 11(a) and 11(b) illustrate the individual inverter utilization in percentage using the min-V and CHMS schemes. As shown in Fig. 11(a), min-V scheme overutilizes the inverters near the beginning of the feeder (BoF) compared to the inverters near the end of feeder (EoF). Specifically, the min-V scheme requires high compensating currents by the inverters near the BoF to minimize harmonic voltage distortions due to the background harmonic voltage and a low grid impedance. However, the overutilization of inverters near the BoF will reduce their expected lifetime compared to inverters near the EoF, resulting to an unfair replacement cost to the inverters' owners. Fig. 11(b) depicts the efficacy of the proposed CHMS scheme to achieve an almost equal utilization of inverters. As shown in Table II, the proposed CHMS scheme improves the average inverters' fairness by 73% compared to min-V, from 0.56 to 0.97, indicating the superiority of CHMS in terms of fairness compared to the min-V scheme.

The average execution time of each method is also listed in Table II. The APF method has a very low complexity since it equally allocates the harmonic currents at the transformer between the inverters. Consequently, its computation time is very low and in average below 0.1 s. The literature-based method min-V requires to solve problem \mathbb{P}^L which is a con-

TABLE III
DIFFERENT OPERATING MODES OF CHMS

Mode	α_s [p.u]	\bar{V}_h [p.u]	Target
M_1	0.10	0.010	Power quality improvement
M_2	0.00	0.060	Transformer lifetime extension
M_3	0.03	0.025	Trade-off solution

TABLE IV
PERFORMANCE OF THE OPERATING MODES, AVERAGE VALUES

Mode	Transf. curr. [A]	THD [%]	Inv. util. [%]	Fairness
No mitig.	37.0	7.8	-	-
M_1	58.0	1.5	25.9	0.96
M_2	3.2	4.7	9.5	0.93
M_3	29.0	3.0	15.1	0.97

vex optimization problem. Therefore, min-V has an average execution time of approximately 0.15 s. The proposed CHMS has higher complexity compared to min-V which is necessary to address the challenge of the fair inverter utilization. The proposed CHMS requires to solve, in average, 9 optimization problems. Problem \mathbb{P}^V is solved once while Problem \mathbb{P}^I is solved in average 8 times, as specified by the iterative Algorithm 1. However, since both Problem \mathbb{P}^V and \mathbb{P}^I are convex optimization problems, the average execution time of the CHMS is still very fast at 1.30 s.

E. Case 3: CHMS Performance Under Different Modes

This case study examines three operating modes, M_1 , M_2 , and M_3 , of the CHMS scheme that have different harmonic compensation priorities. Modes M_1 , M_2 , and M_3 aim to improve the power quality, extend the transformer lifetime, and provide a trade-off solution between power quality improvement and transformer lifetime extension, respectively. Specifically, the harmonic compensation priorities are adjusted by appropriately selecting the harmonic limit of the distribution transformer α_s and the harmonic voltage limit \bar{V}_h . Table III shows the recommended values for α_s and \bar{V}_h for each mode.

Table IV demonstrates the total harmonic current at the transformer, voltage THD, inverter utilization, and fairness for the three operating modes. Considering the mode M_1 , the CHMS scheme improves significantly the power quality by decreasing the average voltage THD from 7.8% to 1.5% V. However, the harmonic current at the distribution transformer increases from 37 A to 58 A, reducing the expected transformer lifetime. Specifically, the harmonic transformer current increases because the background harmonic voltage requires compensating currents to flow into the MV grid to restrain the harmonic voltages within the specified limits \bar{V}_h . Moreover, the reduction of the voltage THD to 1.5% requires a high inverters' utilization (26%), reducing their expected lifetime.

To protect the transformer from the detrimental impacts of harmonic distortion, the operating mode M_2 is used. Considering M_2 with $\alpha_s = 0$, the CHMS scheme decreases the harmonic current at the LV substation by 91%, from 37.0 A to 3.2 A, protecting the transformer. However, mode M_2 presents the highest voltage THD (4.7%) of the three operating modes. Note that mode M_2 requires the selection of a high harmonic voltage limit \bar{V}_h because it does not allow for any harmonic current at the transformer. A low \bar{V}_h in

M_2 will result to a significantly higher inverter utilization with marginal power quality improvement. To enhance the inverters' and transformer expected lifetime, \bar{V}_h should be selected in M_2 according to the maximum allowable values as specified in relevant standards.

A trade-off solution between power quality improvement (M_1) and transformer lifetime extension (M_2) is achieved using the operating mode M_3 . The recommended settings in M_3 (see Table III) allow for a significant improvement of the power quality with a reduction of the voltage THD from 7.8% to 3.0% and a 22% reduction of the harmonic current (from 37 to 29 A) at the transformer with only 15% utilization of the available inverter capacity. As shown in Table IV, the proposed CHMS scheme achieves high fairness values (≥ 0.93) under all the operating modes.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A novel harmonic mitigation strategy considering the particularities of three-phase four-wire networks has been developed to improve the power quality in LVDGs. A three-objectives lexicographic optimization scheme has been formulated to (i) minimize the harmonic voltage limit violations, (ii) maximize the inverter utilization fairness based on Jain's fairness index, and (iii) minimize the compensating currents of the inverters to reduce their lifetime degradation. The original optimization problem is convexified into an SOCP program and a novel algorithm that finds the feasible operating point that maximizes the inverters' utilization fairness is developed. Simulation results demonstrated the capabilities of the proposed CHMS scheme to reduce voltage distortions and protect the distribution transformer in LVDGs. Comparisons with other methodologies highlight the superiority of the proposed method in terms of inverter degradation and inverter utilization fairness, while ensuring a high power quality. Specifically, the proposed scheme outperformed a literature-based strategy by reducing the average and maximum inverters' utilization, while increasing their utilization fairness.

APPENDIX A - LEXICOGRAPHIC OPTIMIZATION

A lexicographic optimization problem optimizes L objective functions, $f_l(\mathbf{x})$ $l = 1, \dots, L$, on a feasible set $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$ in a *lexicographic order* such that $f_l(\mathbf{x})$ has higher priority than $f_{l+1}(\mathbf{x})$ [40]. This implies that objective functions with low priority are optimized as far as does not affect the optimal value of the objective functions with higher priority. The lexicographic optimization problem is stated as

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{lexmin} \{f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_L(\mathbf{x})\} \\ & \text{subject to } \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Commonly, a lexicographic optimization problem can be solved by (i) using the weighted sum method or (ii) solving a sequence of L single-objective optimization problems. The weighted sum method transforms the L objectives problem into an aggregate single-objective problem by introducing weights to the L objectives. Note that there exists a set of weights $\{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_L\}$ where the single-objective problem yields the optimal solution of the lexicographic problem [41]; however, the proper selection of weights is challenging. The most widely-used approach to optimally solve a lexicographic

optimization problem is by solving a sequence of L single-objective optimization problems, ensuring the optimal value of the objectives with higher priority.

Therefore, to derive the solution of problem (A.1), it requires the solution of L optimization subproblems with the l -th one defined as

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize } f_l(\mathbf{x}) \\ & \text{subject to } f_m(\mathbf{x}) \leq f_m(\mathbf{x}_m^*), \quad \forall m \in [1, \dots, l-1], \\ & \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where \mathbf{x}_m^* denotes the optimal solution of subproblem m . The optimal solution of the last optimization subproblem, given by \mathbf{x}_L^* , corresponds to the optimal solution of the lexicographic problem (A.1).

APPENDIX B - NETWORK PARAMETERS

The harmonic impedance matrix, i.e., the impedance matrix at a specific harmonic frequency, of a four-wire 100 mm² Aluminum distribution line in a vertical configuration is given in Table B.I. The parameters of the distribution transformer are $Z_h^t = 0.009 + j0.027h$ p.u, where $h \in \mathcal{H}$ represents the harmonic order.

TABLE B.I
HARMONIC IMPEDANCE MATRIX OF 4x100 mm² ALUMINUM LINE

R (Ohms/km)				X (Ohms/km)			
0.319	0.048	0.048	0.048	0.754h	0.502h	0.439h	0.408h
0.048	0.319	0.048	0.048	0.502h	0.754h	0.502h	0.439h
0.048	0.048	0.319	0.048	0.439h	0.502h	0.754h	0.502h
0.048	0.048	0.048	0.319	0.408h	0.439h	0.502h	0.754h

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Rodríguez-Pajarón, A. Hernández, H. Mendonça, and J. V. Milanović, "Residential harmonic injection models based on field measurements," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 575–587, 2023.
- [2] A. Taghvaie *et al.*, "A comprehensive review of harmonic issues and estimation techniques in power system networks based on traditional and artificial intelligence/machine learning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 31 417–31 442, 2023.
- [3] Y. Wang, J. Yong, Y. Sun, W. Xu, and D. Wong, "Characteristics of harmonic distortions in residential distribution systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 1495–1504, 2017.
- [4] I. Khan, A. S. Vijay, and S. Doolla, "Nonlinear load harmonic mitigation strategies in microgrids: State of the art," *IEEE Syst. J.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 4243–4255, 2022.
- [5] M. T. Au and J. V. Milanovic, "Planning approaches for the strategic placement of passive harmonic filters in radial distribution networks," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 347–353, 2007.
- [6] R. Fonseca Buzo, L. C. O. de Oliveira, and F. B. Leão, "A new method for dimensioning and designing the zero-sequence electromagnetic filter considering system displacement power factor," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 1071–1082, 2020.
- [7] W. U. K. Tareen and S. Mekhief, "Three-phase transformerless shunt active power filter with reduced switch count for harmonic compensation in grid-connected applications," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 4868–4881, 2018.
- [8] X. Liang and C. Bin-Karim, "Harmonics and mitigation techniques through advanced control in grid-connected renewable energy sources: A review," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 3100–3111, 2018.
- [9] E. Ebrahimzadeh *et al.*, "Reducing harmonic instability and resonance problems in PMSG-based wind farms," *IEEE J Emerg. Sel. Topics Power Electron.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 73–83, 2018.
- [10] A. Beiki and M. Rahimi, "Mathematical representation of harmonic resonance phenomenon and harmonic compensation in PMSG based wind farms under feedforward compensation of the grid voltages," *Sustain. Energy Techn. Assessm.*, vol. 57, p. 103162, 2023.

- [11] L. Hadjidemetriou, E. Kyriakides, and F. Blaabjerg, "A robust synchronization to enhance the power quality of renewable energy systems," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 62, no. 8, pp. 4858–4868, 2015.
- [12] Z. Ali *et al.*, "Diversifying the role of distributed generation grid-side converters for improving the power quality of distribution networks using advanced control techniques," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 4110–4123, 2019.
- [13] R. Chilipi *et al.*, "Control of grid-tied multiple distributed generation systems with cooperative compensation capabilities," *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Topics Power Electron.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 821–833, 2022.
- [14] A. Charalambous, L. Hadjidemetriou, and M. Polycarpou, "A sensorless asymmetric and harmonic load compensation method by photovoltaic inverters based on event-triggered impedance estimation," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electr.*, vol. 70, no. 10, pp. 10 089–10 100, 2023.
- [15] A. Kotsionias, M. Asprou, L. Hadjidemetriou, and C. Panayiotou, "Voltage regulation under unbalanced power flow in active four-wire low voltage distribution grids," in *Proc. IEEE ISGT-Europe*, 2022, pp. 1–5.
- [16] R. Nandi *et al.*, "Multi-objective optimization based voltage injection technique for minimizing imbalance and harmonics in AC microgrid," *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 1269–1287, 2024.
- [17] L. Lin *et al.*, "Partitional collaborative mitigation strategy of distribution network harmonics based on distributed model predictive control," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 1998–2009, 2023.
- [18] H. Zhai *et al.*, "An optimal compensation method of shunt active power filters for system-wide voltage quality improvement," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 1270–1281, 2020.
- [19] H. Ebrahimi *et al.*, "Stochastic scheduling of energy storage systems in harmonic polluted active distribution networks," *IET Gener. Transm. Distrib.*, vol. 16, no. 23, pp. 4689–4709, 2022.
- [20] J. Wang *et al.*, "Optimal operation of active distribution network involving the unbalance and harmonic compensation of converter," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5360–5373, 2019.
- [21] X. Xiao, Z. Li, Y. Wang, Y. Zhou, and K. Liu, "Optimal power quality compensation of energy storage system in distribution networks based on unified multi-phase OPF model," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1873–1887, 2022.
- [22] Y. Wang *et al.*, "An efficient approach to power system uncertainty analysis with high-dimensional dependencies," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 2984–2994, 2018.
- [23] J. Meyer, A.-M. Blanco, M. Domagk, and P. Schegner, "Assessment of prevailing harmonic current emission in public low-voltage networks," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 962–970, 2017.
- [24] R. de Barros *et al.*, "Lifetime evaluation of a multifunctional PV single-phase inverter during harmonic current compensation," *Microelectron. Rel.*, vol. 88–90, pp. 1071–1076, 2018.
- [25] R. Jain *et al.*, "A quantitative measure of fairness and discrimination for resource allocation in shared computer systems," Digital Equipment Corporation, Tech. Rep. DEC-TR-301, 1984.
- [26] S. Schwarz, C. Mehlhruher, and M. Rupp, "Throughput maximizing multiuser scheduling with adjustable fairness," in *Proc. IEEE Intern. Conf. Commun. (ICC)*, 2011, pp. 1–5.
- [27] C. Guo *et al.*, "Throughput maximization with short-term and long-term Jain's index constraints in downlink OFDMA systems," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 62, no. 5, pp. 1503–1517, 2014.
- [28] M. Z. Liu *et al.*, "On the fairness of PV curtailment schemes in residential distribution networks," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 4502–4512, 2020.
- [29] M. Houwing *et al.*, "A reputation management system for the fair utilization of community energy storage systems," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 582–592, 2023.
- [30] A. Hussain *et al.*, "Fairness and utilitarianism in allocating energy to EVs during power contingencies using modified division rules," *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1444–1456, 2022.
- [31] W. Rodrigues *et al.*, "Low voltage smart meter for monitoring of power quality disturbances applied in smart grid," *Measurement*, vol. 147, 2019.
- [32] L. Hadjidemetriou, E. Kyriakides, Y. Yang, and F. Blaabjerg, "A synchronization method for single-phase grid-tied inverters," *IEEE Trans. Power Electr.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 2139–2149, 2016.
- [33] G. C. Kryonidis *et al.*, "Ancillary services in active distribution networks: A review of technological trends from operational and online analysis perspective," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 147, p. 111198, 2021.
- [34] A. Estebarsari *et al.*, "IoT-enabled real-time management of smart grids with demand response aggregators," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 102–112, 2022.
- [35] "IEEE standard definitions for the measurement of electric power quantities under sinusoidal, nonsinusoidal, balanced, or unbalanced conditions," *IEEE Std 1459-2010 (Revision of IEEE Std 1459-2000)*, pp. 1–50, 2010.
- [36] N. Rezaeinia *et al.*, "On efficiency and the Jain's fairness index in integer assignment problems," *Comput. Manage. Sci.*, vol. 20, 2023.
- [37] Gurobi Optimization, LLC. Gurobi optimizer reference manual, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://www.gurobi.com>
- [38] H. L. Willis, *Power Distribution Planning Reference Book*, 2nd ed. New York, NY, USA: CRC Press, 2004.
- [39] X. Xiao, Z. Li, Y. Wang, and Y. Zhou, "A practical approach to estimate harmonic distortions in residential distribution system," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 1418–1427, 2021.
- [40] L. Tziouvani *et al.*, "Energy management and control of a flywheel storage system for peak shaving applications," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 4195–4207, 2021.
- [41] H. D. Sherali and A. L. Soyster, "Preemptive and nonpreemptive multi-objective programming: Relationship and counterexamples," *J. Optim. Theory Appl.*, vol. 39, pp. 173–186, 1983.

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